

Fundamental and Technical Analysis of It Companies Included In Nifty It Index

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Abstract

As it is evident that the mobility of people has hampered to a great extent by the pandemic. This leads to the need of digitalization. Digitalization is the mode which, despite of the lacuna inherent in it, helps the country in maintaining its pace. Now, in today's time the country has become the digitalization hub. It is inevitable in the functioning of financial market also. It helps in making the trading more convenient and paperless. This research work analyzes the work which has already been done regarding the fundamental and technical analysis of the companies. This work substantially focuses on the examination of effectiveness of the tools and techniques of aforementioned analysis that can be used by the investors in making their investment profitable.

Introduction

This research is designed to examine the tools and techniques of fundamental analysis and technical analysis. Fundamental analysis helps determine the intrinsic value of a stock which takes into consideration the financial statements, events and industry trends. The tools and techniques of fundamental analysis are used to determine the key attributes and worth of a company. It includes economic analysis, industry analysis and company analysis. On the other hand, technical analysis is

concerned with the analysis of stock price and volume of trade to predict future price movement. Tools in technical analysis are used in such a manner that they examine how demand and supply for a stock influence its price and volume of trade. Both these analyses are useful for making investment decisions.

The present chapter discusses the concept of the Indian financial system, financial markets, secondary market, SEBI, stock exchanges i.e. BSE and NSE, and their indices.

A financial system is a system of financial markets, financial institutions, financial assets, and financial services. It involves the exchange of funds between those who invest funds and those who utilise funds. **Financial markets** are the markets where people trade in financial securities and derivatives. It includes the money market and capital market. **The money market** is the short-term market where short-term funds are traded whose maturity period is less than a year. The Reserve bank of India is responsible for the working of the money market which comprises government securities (t-bills, call money), and corporate securities (commercial papers, certificate of deposits). **The capital market** is the market for long-term securities in which securities with a maturity period of more than

a year are traded. The securities and exchange board of India is the controller of the capital market in India. Capital markets are further classified as primary and secondary markets. In **primary markets**, newly issued securities are offered for example initial public offer (IPO) and follow-up public offer (FPO) whereas in **the secondary market** already issued securities are traded publically. The secondary market is driven by market forces of demand and supply.

Financial institutions act as a connecting pin between lenders and borrowers. These institutions are the mediators who link the parties involved in a financial transaction. Financial intermediaries are another name for **financial institutions**. These can

be classified into two categories that are banking institutions and non-banking institutions.

Banking institutions include:

1. Commercial banks
2. Co-operative banks
3. Regional rural banks
4. Foreign banks

Financial instruments are the assets that represent a legal agreement involving some monetary value. It can be a real or virtual asset that can be traded in financial markets. For example equity, debentures, treasury bills, commercial papers, etc. **Financial services** are the services provided by the financial sector that includes banking, insurance, investment banking, foreign exchange services, etc.

The securities and exchange board of India is the regulator of the capital market in India. It was established on 12 April 1988 and was given statutory powers on 30 January 1992 through SEBI Act, 1992. It has its headquarters in Mumbai, India. It regulates both primary and secondary markets. Its objective is to protect the rights of investors and promote, regulate, and develop the secondary market. It regulates stock exchanges. Two major stock exchanges in India are the **Bombay stock exchange** popularly known as **BSE** and the **National stock exchange (NSE)**.

Bombay stock exchange is the oldest stock exchange in Asia which was established in 1875. It is situated in Mumbai, Maharashtra. It is the fastest stock exchange in the world with a speed of 6 microseconds. NSE's index is known as **S&P BSE SENSEX**. The other indexes are S&P BSE 50, S&P BSE Sensex next 50, S&P BSE 100, etc.

The national stock exchange, established in 1992 is the first dematerialized stock exchange in India that provides a fully automated screen-based electronic trading system. It is located in Mumbai, Maharashtra. In 2021 it is the world's largest derivatives exchange by the number of contracts. NSE's index is NIFTY 50 which consists of 50 stock indices. It is launched by NSE in 1996. NSE also has sectoral indices for example nifty bank index, Nifty auto index, nifty FMCG index, nifty IT index, nifty media index, etc.

Investment

The whole financial system talks about investments. When a person, who has extra money than required, invests his extra cash in securities or other assets this is called investment. Investment is of mechanism which is used for generating future profits, which can be in terms of future regular income or terms of capital appreciation.

The investment could be done in

1. Real assets
2. Financial assets
3. Commodity assets

Investment process

This investment requires a series of activities to be performed. Generally, it is a five-step process including investment policy, security analysis, valuation of securities, construction of portfolio and valuation of the portfolio.

1. Investment policy:

The first step in the process of the investment process is deciding the investment policy. It includes the determination of investible funds, the objective of investments and the knowledge regarding alternatives and markets.

2. Security analysis:

This step involves analysis of individual securities and overall market analysis. Security analysis involves:

1. Fundamental analysis
2. Technical analysis
3. Risk and return analysis
4. Efficient market hypothesis

3. Valuation of securities:

This step involves the calculation of the value of securities; the present worth of securities to the investor is considered and compared to the current market price.

4. Construction of portfolio:

A portfolio is a combination of various securities in such a way that it fulfils the investor's objective. A portfolio is constructed to reduce the risk to the minimum level and to maximize the profits of the investor.

5. Valuation of portfolio:

This is the last step of the investment process. In this step, the value of the portfolio is ascertained. The portfolio has to be managed efficiently. This process consists of regular management and evaluation of the portfolio.

Security analysis

Analysing the securities before investing is a very crucial step. This step helps in making decisions on whether to buy or sell securities by indicating possible market trends. Analysing securities involves fundamental analysis, technical analysis, risk and return analysis and efficient market hypothesis. A brief explanation of fundamental and technical analysis is as follows.

Fundamental analysis is the assessment of a business's financial statements which facilitates the investors in making investment decisions. It is used to determine the intrinsic value of the stock. Furthermore, it helps in analysing the company's health, profitability and liquidity. Again it is a useful source to form an opinion on the overall state of the economy and macroeconomic factors including interest rate, employment, GDP, manufacturing and management.

Fundamental analysis can be done with either a **top-down approach** or a **bottom-up approach**.

When an investor follows a top-down approach analysis starts with the analysis of the overall economy by analysing various macro-economic factors like gross domestic product, inflation, interest rates, etc. Followed by the analysis of the industry where the performance of the whole industry is taken into consideration. And at last, analyzing the company's financial performance by analyzing its earnings per share, dividend yield ratio, dividend payout ratio, and return on equity. Whereas in the bottom-up approach investor initially analyse companies followed by industry analysis and economic analysis.

Phases of fundamental analysis:

1. **Economic analysis:** In economic analysis, the overall health of the economy is analyzed. How the economy is performing directly impacts the performance of a company so it is very important to analyze the economic conditions. If the economy is growing then it will offer a positive environment for the company to grow. In the same way, if the economy is showing signs of recession it will be hard for a company to perform well.
2. **Industry analysis:** Industry analysis involves analysis of the performance of that industry by identifying of demand and supply gap, the competitiveness existing in the industry, government regulations, production factors, etc. The stage of growth of many industries can be classified into three stages i.e. pioneer stage, expansion stage and growth stage
3. **Company analysis:** Company analysis is an important part of fundamental analysis. It involved analyzing a company's balance sheet, cash flow statement, and financial ratios. Profitability ratios are calculated to calculate the intrinsic value of the stock.

Tools used in company analysis:

1. EARNINGS PER SHARE;
2. PRICE TO BOOK RATIO;
3. DIVIDEND YIELD RATIO;
4. DIVIDEND PAYOUT RATIO;
5. PRICE TO SALES RATIO;
6. RETURN ON EQUITY.

Technical analysis, in its scope, is used to forecast the price movement of different securities with the understanding of past market data, primary price and volume. It helps in analysing the market trend for availing the benefits of trading opportunities. Technical analysis includes the study of past prices and volume to find out trends and predict future price movements. Technical analysis uses various indicators which indicate possible fluctuations in the stock market. It uses historical data to predict future prices.

Tools and techniques used in technical analysis:

1. Trend lines
2. Support and resistance levels
3. Moving averages
4. Chart pattern
5. Candlestick chart
6. Trading volumes
7. Oscillators

Literature Review

P. Prakash And S. Sundararajan. (2016) in their paper titled “**An Analytical Research On Fundamental And Technical Analysis Of Icici Bank Stocks In India**” performed analytical research that deals with the facts and data related to the stock prices of ICICI bank. For the purpose of fundamental research, company analysis has been done with the help of ratio analysis. And for technical analysis, tools such as Beta analysis, Relative strength index (RSI), and rate of change (ROC) have been employed. The stock market is very volatile and is very important to have its knowledge for making a profit. The researchers concluded that the fundamental and technical analysis helps the investor in wisely investing their funds.

Bulow, Staffan. (2017) studied in their research headed “**The Effectiveness Of Fundamental Analysis On Value Stocks-An Analysis Of Piotroski's F-Score**” replicates Piotroski's f-score model of investment on the US market for a period of 9 years starting from 2003 to 2015. The results have shown that the portfolio with a higher f-score earns a return of 18.3% annually whereas the portfolio with a lower f-score earns a 4% of annual return. The significant mean difference in the return of the portfolios of 14.3% indicates that fundamental analysis is useful in determining the winner and loser stocks. The author also noticed that the best benefit of this investment strategy can be found in small and medium firms. Behavioural finance perception also acts as a supporting hand in the success of this strategy. Furthermore, value stocks were been abandoned by the investors due to cognitive biases and fundamental analysis can use this by finding financially strong firms in an unbiased manner.

S, Shilpa K, J, Arya Mol And Ambily A.S (2017) in their paper named “**The Study On Fundamental Analysis Of Selected It Companies Listed At Nse**” studied the performance of IT companies and fundamental analysis of selected five companies and found out the intrinsic value of their shares. Mainly secondary data has been used in the research. The fundamental analysis has been done in three stages namely, economic analysis, industry analysis and company analysis. The tools used in economic analysis were GDP, inflation, fiscal deficit, current account deficit, etc whereas, for industry analysis,

government preference, entry barriers and porter's five force model were used. For the company analysis, various ratios were used for example; dividend payout ratio, EPS, P/E ratio and debt to equity ratio were used to calculate the intrinsic value of the share and to find out whether the stocks are undervalued or overvalued. Five years of economic data i.e. from 2011-12 to 2015-2016 have been collected and the data of five companies (WIPRO, INFOSYS, TCS, MINDTREE and HCL TECH) were taken for company analysis. After the detailed analysis, the researcher found that the intrinsic value of shares of WIPRO, INFOSYS and TCS is more than their market price (i.e. shares are underpriced) so the authors recommend that investors should hold or buy the stocks of these companies as the market is expected to increase in future. On the other hand, the intrinsic value of shares is less than their market price (i.e. shares are overpriced) therefore, the market share prices of MINDTREE and HCL TECH are expected to fall in the future. So, the investors should sell the shares of these companies. The study recommends that investors should have IT sector companies in their portfolio as it is one of the most promising sectors of the economy. IT sector companies are expected to give significant returns on their investment.

Uthami Wiwik, Nugroho Lucky, Farida. (2017). has researched the topic **Fundamental Versus Technical Analysis Of Investment: Case Study Of Investors Decision In Indonesia Stock Exchange.** **Journal Of Internet Banking And Commerce** to know the preference of investors in the selection of the method for stock analysis and also to evaluate the factors affecting their choice. The research is mainly based on the primary data collected from 125 participants by way of a questionnaire. The researchers have used six independent variables (investor's education, investor's experience, information accessibility, investor's time horizon, frequency of trading activities, and investor's perception towards the disclosure) to know the choice of investors. The research has concluded that investors in Indonesia prefer technical analysis to forecast future stock prices. The research also found that the most influential factor in selecting methods are the investor's experience and the investor's time horizon. The other four factors have not been found significant in influencing the investor's choice namely, investor's education, information accessibility, frequency of trading activities and investor's perception towards disclosure.

The researchers have also given some recommendations that as an investor's experience is a significant factor in choosing the methods of analysis, inexperienced investors should not be discouraged from investing. It has been found that the investor's time span for investing is generally

less than a year but the investors should not rush in taking decisions for avoiding loss. However, other factors might not be significant but the investor should seek knowledge regarding investments. The researchers have also suggested that further research can be conducted by adding more variables.

Jayaprakash, Rinu.(2017). An Analysis Of The Performance Of Nifty Infrastructure Index Stocks. The study aimed to analyse the current pricing of stocks with respect to the NIFTY index, predict investor position, and develop and suggest a portfolio of profitable infrastructure stocks. The study concludes that in the current scenario undervalued stocks are the best-buying stocks. The technical analysis provides the rationale investor the right time to buy or sell the stocks.

Soni Shriprakash And Chandak Govind in 2017 published a research paper on the **Fundamental Analysis Of Car Manufacturing Companies In India.** The research was based on the analysis of the profitability position of Indian car manufacturing companies and their comparative analysis. This research used secondary data in form of balance sheets and other data from websites. The top five car manufacturing companies were selected as samples namely, TATA Motors DVR, Maruti Suzuki India, Mahindra CIE Automotive, SML-Isuzu, and Force India by purposive sampling technique.

The variables which have been considered in the study are:

1. Operating Profit Margin(OPM)
2. Net Profit Margin (NPM)
3. Return On Equity (ROE)
4. Earnings Per Share(EPS)
5. Price-Earnings Ratio(PER)
6. Dividends Per Share(DPS)
7. Dividends Payout Ratio (DPR)

The study was conducted for the time period of 10 years i.e. from 2006-07 to 2015-16 10. Statistical tools used in the analysis of the data are arithmetic mean (average), standard deviation (SD), one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA), and compound annual growth rate (CAGR). The research concluded that each company is better than the other on different criteria. For example, Maruti Suzuki is better than other companies in parameters like DPM, ROC, and NPM, whereas Force Motors performed better in parameters like EPS. The researchers also found that there was a significant difference between the net profit margin and the dividend payout ratio in all five companies. After conducting the research, the researchers suggest that investors to invest in Force Motors as its Earning Per Share is the maximum among all five companies.

J, Vinutha (2018). A Study On Technical Analysis Of Selected Stocks Of Nifty Fifty" Research with the objective of studying sample stocks using technical analysis by using techniques

of moving average and rate of change and to forecast future trends. Five companies of NIFTY are selected as samples. Secondary data is collected for a period of 24 months. The study concluded that RSI charts are very helpful in predicting future price movement.

Sharma, Varsha And Biyani, Sanjay (2019) Have Researched The Topic “**A Study On Fundamental Analysis: Evidence From Selected Indian It Stocks**”. The objective of the study was to analyze the performance of the IT sector in India and to conduct a fundamental analysis of major IT companies. The study was purely based on the IT companies listed in NSE and BSE and based on their performance, revenue and market capitalization top five companies were selected as sample, namely, TCS, WIPRO, HCL, TECH Mahendra and INFOSYS. As fundamental analysis is done in three stages, factors used for economic analysis were GDP, inflation, current account, fiscal deficit and the unemployment rate for five years i.e. 2014-2018. For industry analysis, market size and government initiatives were taken into account. Lastly, for analyzing the performance of a particular company, their earning per share ratio, profitability ratio, net profit margin, return on capital employed, quick ratio etc were analyzed. The research concluded that the IT sector plays an important role in the growth of the economy and GDP. TCS was analyzed as the market leader whereas, HCL and INFOSYS were growing companies. The researchers concluded that information technology was the rising sector in the investment market.

P. Devika. (2019). A Study On Fundamental Analysis Of Automobile Companies (Car Manufacturing Companies) In India evaluated the profitability position and fundamentals of the car manufacturing companies in India.

T Venkata Swapna, S. Subbalakshmi.(2020) In Their Paper Headed “**A Study On Fundamental Analysis Of Selected Stocks Of It Sector**” have analyzed the performance and trends of the selected stocks of companies in IT sector. The researchers have also examined the risk and return of selected stocks. For the purpose of the sample, five companies were selected namely, Mastek, Mphasis, Mucleus, Zensartec and Sonatsoft. Secondary data was used for fundamental analysis from newspapers, the internet, and journals. Risk, Returns, Variance, Coefficient of variance, P/E ratio and I/E ratio are the statistical tools used in the research. The researchers concluded that fundamental analysis helps in calculating the intrinsic value of the stocks. The dividend discount model is a widely used model for determining the intrinsic value of stocks. Indian IT industry is the most frequently growing sector and showing growth. It is difficult to understand whether the return prediction is reflecting risk or is

mispriced. This can be simplified by analyzing the consistency of return prediction with a reasonable risk model.

Detzel Andrew, Liu Hong, Strauss Jack, Zhou Guoth, Zhu Yinhzi. (2020) In Their Paper Titled “**Learning And Predictability Via Technical Analysis: Evidence From Bitcoin And Stocks With Hard To Value Fundamentals**” studied how technical analysis is helpful in predicting the future price movements of assets with hard to value fundamentals, for example, Bitcoin, Cryptocurrencies and stocks of a new company with a limited fundamental available. They also used price to moving average ratio of daily Bitcoin prices to analyze bitcoin returns. For conducting research the researchers have taken daily Bitcoin prices in different stock exchanges in the world as data and analyzed them. The researchers concluded that the future price movements and trade volume is predictable by using the moving average of price. Simple real-time strategies can be adopted to make buy and sell decisions based on the prediction. Price to moving average ratio is also helpful in forecasting the return on the stocks. The researchers also stated that similar results can be concluded for small-cap, young firms and low-analyst coverage stocks.

Singh, Shalini & Chakraborty, Anindita (2022). Stock Price Movement Through Technical Analysis: Empirical Evidence From The Information Technology (It) Sector. The research was conducted to analyze the trends in price movement in IT companies and analyze it using technical analysis. The researcher used secondary data to reach the conclusion that fundamental analysis should also be suggested along with technical analysis to reach to investing decision. The risk and return ratio should also be calculated before performing technical analysis.

Conclusion:

1. From the study of the literature review it is concluded that fundamental analysis is used to calculate the intrinsic value of the share. The dividend discount model is extensively used for fundamental analysis. The investor should invest in the company with higher EPS. Investor should buy undervalued stocks which have intrinsic value more than its market price. Technical analysis is very effective in securities analysis.
2. Price and trading volume can be predicted using moving average of price. Price to moving average ratio helps in forecasting the returns on the securities. Technical analysis helps to predict the future price movement efficiently.
3. Both the analysis help investors in stock analysis and works best when used simultaneously.

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